

Moving a Traditional Assessment into the Next Generation: Exploring the Road Ahead

Research Background: Importance of Clinical Judgement (CJ)

- NCSBN & American Institutes of Research (AIR) collaboration
 - Identify the core RN requirements
 - Gather updated list of job duties and tasks
 - Document examples of tools and equipment as supporting evidence for the ability requirements
- Methods:
 - Functional Job Analysis
 - Strategic Job Analysis
 - Health care facility site visits
 - Job analysis survey
 - Linkage workshop
 - Rate cross-tab of KSA and tasks by job duty

Areas of Observation & Documentation

Job Requirement	Definition	Job Requirement	Definition
Duties	Collections of work activities that have a common objective.	Abilities	Traits workers possess that give them the capacity to carry out physical and mental acts required by a job's tasks.
Tasks	Specific work activities performed for a specific purpose.	Other Personal Characteristics	Any other personal attributes (e.g., personality traits, attitudes, work styles, values) that are required to perform the job.
Knowledge	Body of factual, technical, or procedural information a worker uses to perform a job.	Tools and Equipment	Objects used by workers to complete job tasks.
Skills	The capacity, developed through training or practice, to perform job tasks.	Key Judgments & Consequences of Error	Decisions workers make to complete job tasks; consequences of making a decision error.

Summary of Research

Representation Across Data Collection Efforts	Functional Job Analysis (RNs)	Strategic Job Analysis (RNs)
Total N of Job Experts	2,522 SMEs	90 SMEs
Number of Practice Care Settings	24 Practice Care Settings	20 Practice Care Settings
Number of Geographic Regions	All 4 Geographic Regions	All 4 Geographic Regions
Number of States	55 States and/or U.S. Territories	33 States
Range of Tenure	0 months - 45 years	2 years - 45 years

Linkage Example: 50 RN Experts Rated

		RN Tasks for Duty E				
		E1	E2	E3	E4	
<p><i>To what extent is the knowledge required in order to accomplish the task?</i></p> <p>0 – Not Relevant for Performing the Task 1 – Helpful for Performing the Task 2 – Essential for Performing the Task DK – Don't Know</p>		<p>Discuss reproductive or sexual issues with client, such as family planning, menopause, erectile dysfunction, or gender identity.</p>	<p>Identify client immunization needs.</p>	<p>Perform routine, comprehensive health assessment.</p>	<p>Perform a targeted screening assessments, such as scoliosis, hearing, or vision.</p>	
Knowledge Statements		Knowledge Topics				
1	Case Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of case manager • Documentation to support reimbursement (e.g., saline flushes, skin assessment) 				
2	Client Prioritization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Severity of common medical conditions • Time sensitivity of procedures, treatments, and medication administrations 				
3	Conflict Resolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process • Techniques (e.g., combatting lateral violence) 				

Result: Highest Rated Skills Needed

Skill	Skill Definition
Clinical Judgment	Skill in recognizing cues about a clinical situation, generating and weighing hypotheses, taking action, and evaluating outcomes for the purpose of arriving at a satisfactory clinical outcome. Clinical judgment is the observed outcome of two unobserved underlying mental processes, critical thinking and decision making.
Professional Communication	Skill in communicating in a clear, concise, and effective manner, and adapting one's own communication style to meet the needs of the health care team, clients, family, and/or caregivers, and situation.
Active Listening	Skill in giving full attention to what is said, taking time to understand the points made, asking questions as appropriate, and asking clarifying questions and repeating back what the client, family, caregiver, and/or health care team member said.

Importance of Clinical Judgement

S32 Critical Thinking
S33 Clinical Judgement
S34 Problem Solving

NCLEX: RN Licensure Exam

- Currently NCLEX assesses KSAs associate to entry-level nursing
- Items measure both content areas & aspects of the nursing process
- However, direct assessment of CJ is not a focus of the exam, but there are items that represent CJ in the bank

- Main Question:
Can we explicitly measure CJ that is appropriate for an entry-level RN, i.e. within the 1st year of clinical practice

Turning results into actionable test development

MOVING FORWARD

Defining and Measuring the Clinical Judgement Construct

Defining the Construct

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Operational Definition of Clinical Judgement

Clinical judgement is defined as the observed outcome of critical thinking and decision-making. It is an iterative process that uses nursing knowledge to observe and assess presenting situations, identify a prioritized client concern and generate the best possible evidence-based solutions in order to deliver safe client care.

Conceptual Model: Uses Ideas from All Current CJ accepted in Nursing

- Focus on entry-level → Novice level of judgment skill (Skills Acquisition/Humanistic model)
- Novice level individuals tend to
 - Have rules based, discipline specific understanding
 - Experts tend to have highly organized content knowledge reflecting deep understanding
 - Rely on facts and features of the discipline/domain to guide behavior/actions
 - Experts tend to have knowledge that is conditioned on a set of circumstances
 - Less likely to notice meaningful patterns due to lack of experience/exposure
 - Tend to spend more time analyzing situations than deliberating what action to take
 - Less able to monitor own performance, i.e. metacognition
 - Experts tend to be able to monitor their own understanding and recognize when it is not adequate
 - Less able to detect problems and spot anomalies as a situation unfolds

Cognitive Theory of the Construct

Clinical Judgement

- Because of the nature of novice level → Information Processing model provides a basis for operationalizing the rules based, discipline specific decision-making process
- Cognitive constructs underlying IP model:
 - Cue recognition
 - Cue interpretation
 - Hypotheses generation
 - Hypotheses evaluation
 - Generate solutions
 - Take action
 - Evaluate outcomes

Initial Operationalization of the Cognitive Structure of the Construct

Identifying a Cognitive Model of the Clinical Judgement Construct:

- Translating the Nursing Process Model into a Decision-making Model

Current Clinical Judgement Conceptual Model

Focus for Task/Item Development

Layer 3

Layer 4

Conceptual Definitions

RECOGNIZE CUES

Filtering information from different sources (e.g., signs, symptoms, medical history)

- What information is relevant/irrelevant?
- What information is most important
- What is of immediate concern?

Do not connect cues with any hypotheses just yet.

Conceptual Definitions

ANALYZE CUES

Organizing and linking the recognized cues to the client's clinical presentation

- What client conditions are consistent with the cues?
- Are there cues that support or contraindicate a particular condition?
- Why is a particular cue or subset of cues of concern?

Focus on a multitude of things that could be happening. Narrowing things down comes at the next step.

Conceptual Definitions

PRIORITIZE HYPOTHESES

Evaluating and ranking hypotheses according to priority (urgency, likelihood, risk, difficulty, time, etc.).

- Which explanations are most/least likely?
- Which possible explanations are the most serious?

Evaluating a hypothesis should include justification (i.e., the why).

Ranking will typically uses phrases like "most likely."

Conceptual Definitions

GENERATE SOLUTIONS

Identifying expected outcomes and using hypotheses to define a set of interventions for the expected outcomes.

- What are the desirable outcomes?
- What interventions can achieve those outcomes?
- What should be avoided?
- If needed, what additional information would be most valuable?

Avoid cementing the Plan of Care with exactly what to do.

Focus instead on goals and multiple possible interventions—not just the best one--that connect to those goals.

Conceptual Definitions

TAKE ACTION

Implementing the solution(s) that addresses the highest priorities.

- Which intervention or combination of interventions is most appropriate?
- How should the intervention(s) be accomplished (performed, requested, administered, communicated, taught, documented, etc.)?

If the steps in a process are the focus, ensure judgment rather than recall is needed.

The item stem and/or the responses should include action verbs.

Conceptual Definitions

EVALUATE OUTCOMES

Comparing observed outcomes against expected outcomes.

- What signs point to getting better/worse/same?
- Were the interventions effective?
- Would other interventions have been more effective?

Item development should focus on the efficacy of the intervention(s) from the previous items.

Pilot Study on Clinical Judgment

VALIDATION MODEL

Pilot Study: Objectives

- Evaluate relationship between CJ and Knowledge items
- Investigate responding probabilities between clinical judgment conditions
- Is CJ more difficult than Knowledge items?
- What is the relationship between response probabilities for the 2 different types of items?
 - Is CJ something over and above knowledge?

Pilot Study: Methods

Factor 1:
Content Area

55 Subdomains

Factor 2:
Item Response
Format

Multiple Choice

Multiple Response

Factor 3:
Item Assessment

3,100 Examinees

Pilot Study: Results

Pilot Study: Results

Pilot Study: Results

Pilot Study: Results

Pilot Study: Discussion

- Conclusion
 - Responding probabilities differ across
 - Content subdomains
 - Item response formats
 - Established an asymmetric relationship between knowledge and CJ
- Future Directions
 - Multiple-observation assessment
 - Multiple replications